

One local basis separates every countable state family

Hyunho Cha and Jungwoo Lee

NextQuantum and Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Seoul National University, Seoul 08826, Republic of Korea

{ovalavo, junglee}@snu.ac.kr

Abstract

In quantum theory, tomography addresses the problem of identifying an unknown state from the probabilities assigned to measurement outcomes. Understanding how much measurement data is needed for state identification is a fundamental question in tomography, and the answer depends on both the allowed state model and the allowed measurement structure. In multipartite systems, it was not known whether a constant number of local product bases suffices to distinguish all algebraic n -qubit pure states. We show the more general result that every fixed countable family of n -qubit states can be separated by *one* suitably chosen local product basis. Thus informational completeness for algebraic states admits a stronger local form than previously known. The result shows that for separation of algebraic or otherwise countable state models, locality by itself is not an obstruction.

1 Introduction

Quantum state tomography asks how to determine an unknown quantum state from measurement probabilities. A pure state is represented by a unit vector ψ in a complex Hilbert space, with the convention that multiplying ψ by a complex number of absolute value 1 gives the same physical state. If $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_D\}$ is an orthonormal basis, then measuring ψ in the basis B gives the Born probability vector $(|\langle b_1, \psi \rangle|^2, \dots, |\langle b_D, \psi \rangle|^2)$. For the full set of pure states, one basis is plainly insufficient because it determines only the absolute values of the coordinates of ψ in that basis, not all relative phases.

The situation is different when the possible states are restricted in an arithmetic way. A natural and important example is the family of pure states whose computational-basis coordinates are algebraic numbers. For each fixed number of qubits, the corresponding family of algebraic pure states is countable, although it remains dense in the set of all pure states. This makes it possible for a suitably chosen measurement to avoid all pairwise collisions among the allowed states.

This work studies that phenomenon under the additional locality constraint that is natural for multipartite systems. For n qubits, a local product measurement basis is a basis of $(\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$ obtained by choosing one ordinary two-outcome orthonormal basis independently on each qubit and then taking the tensor-product basis. The local-basis question considered here is whether there exists a number m independent of n such that for each n , there are m local product orthonormal bases of $(\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$ whose outcome probability distributions uniquely determine every algebraic n -qubit pure state up to global phase.

Our main result gives a strong affirmative answer to this question of informational completeness. For every positive integer n , there exists one local product orthonormal basis of $(\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$ whose measurement probabilities distinguish every pair of distinct algebraic pure states. In fact,

the proof establishes the more general statement that every *countable* family of *density matrices* in a finite tensor-product Hilbert space can be separated by one suitably chosen local product basis.

This perspective also connects with recent work of Feng et al. [1]. They proved that two measurement bases are informationally complete for algebraic pure states. Their general construction uses entangled bases, and they explicitly identified the sufficiency of a constant number of local bases for algebraic pure states as an open question. This work resolves the question in the affirmative, and does so with a *single* local product basis.

This does not contradict lower bounds for unrestricted pure-state tomography. Such lower bounds concern the full, uncountable set of pure states (see, for example, [2, 3]). A single basis cannot distinguish all pure states. However, the set of algebraic pure states, and more generally any fixed countable state family, has only countably many distinct pairs, so a single measurement can avoid all corresponding pairwise collisions simultaneously.

2 Notations

A finite-dimensional complex Hilbert space is a finite-dimensional vector space H over \mathbb{C} , equipped with an inner product

$$\langle u, v \rangle \in \mathbb{C}.$$

A qubit has Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^2 . Its standard basis vectors are denoted

$$|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

For n qubits the Hilbert space is

$$H_n = (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}.$$

For a bit string $s = s_1 \cdots s_n \in \{0, 1\}^n$, the computational-basis vector is

$$|s\rangle = |s_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |s_n\rangle.$$

The dimension of H_n is $D = 2^n$.

A pure quantum state is a one-dimensional subspace, or ray, of H . Equivalently, it is represented by a unit vector $\psi \in H$, with the convention that ψ and $e^{i\theta}\psi$ represent the same physical state for every real θ . For a unit vector ψ , define

$$|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| : H \rightarrow H, \quad |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|(v) = \psi \langle\psi, v\rangle.$$

This operator is the density matrix of the pure state represented by ψ . Let ψ and ϕ be unit vectors in a finite-dimensional Hilbert space. Then

$$|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| = |\phi\rangle\langle\phi| \iff \psi = e^{i\theta}\phi \text{ for some real } \theta.$$

Let $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_D\}$ be an orthonormal basis of H . Measuring the pure state ψ in basis B gives outcome probabilities

$$p_B(\psi) = (|\langle b_1, \psi \rangle|^2, \dots, |\langle b_D, \psi \rangle|^2).$$

The basis B is informationally complete with respect to a set S of pure states if

$$p_B(\psi) = p_B(\phi) \quad \text{and} \quad \psi, \phi \in S \implies |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| = |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|.$$

For n qubits, a local product orthonormal basis is a basis of H_n of the form

$$B = B_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes B_n,$$

where each $B_j = \{u_{j,0}, u_{j,1}\}$ is an orthonormal basis of the j -th copy of \mathbb{C}^2 . Its basis vectors are

$$u_{1,x_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes u_{n,x_n}, \quad x = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \{0, 1\}^n.$$

For a finite-dimensional Hilbert space H , $\text{Herm}(H)$ denotes the real vector space of Hermitian linear operators on H .

3 Algebraic numbers and countability

Definition 1. A complex number z is algebraic if there is a nonzero polynomial

$$f(X) = a_0 + a_1X + \cdots + a_mX^m$$

with rational coefficients $a_j \in \mathbb{Q}$ such that $f(z) = 0$. The set of algebraic complex numbers is denoted $\overline{\mathbb{Q}}$. A complex number that is not algebraic is transcendental.

Definition 2. An n -qubit pure state is algebraic if it has a unit-vector representative

$$\psi = \sum_{s \in \{0,1\}^n} c_s |s\rangle$$

such that every coefficient c_s is algebraic.

The set $\overline{\mathbb{Q}}$ of algebraic complex numbers is countable, and for fixed n , the set of algebraic n -qubit pure states is also countable.

Definition 3. Let $K \subseteq \mathbb{C}$ be a field. Real numbers t_1, \dots, t_m are algebraically independent over K if no nonzero polynomial $P \in K[X_1, \dots, X_m]$ satisfies

$$P(t_1, \dots, t_m) = 0.$$

Lemma 1. Let $K \subseteq \mathbb{C}$ be a countable field and let m be a positive integer. There exist real numbers t_1, \dots, t_m that are algebraically independent over K .

Proof. We choose t_1, \dots, t_m one at a time.

Assume t_1, \dots, t_{j-1} have already been chosen algebraically independent over K , with $j = 1$ meaning that none have yet been chosen. Let

$$L = K(t_1, \dots, t_{j-1})$$

be the field obtained by adjoining the already chosen numbers. Elements of L are ratios of polynomials in t_1, \dots, t_{j-1} with coefficients in K , with nonzero denominator. There are only countably many such ratios because K is countable and there are only countably many finite polynomials with coefficients in K . Hence L is countable.

The set of complex numbers algebraic over L is countable by the same proof as the countability of $\overline{\mathbb{Q}}$, replacing \mathbb{Q} by the countable field L . Since \mathbb{R} is uncountable, there is a real number t_j that is not algebraic over L . Choose such a t_j .

We claim t_1, \dots, t_j are algebraically independent over K . If not, some nonzero polynomial

$$P(X_1, \dots, X_j) \in K[X_1, \dots, X_j]$$

would satisfy $P(t_1, \dots, t_j) = 0$. View this as a polynomial in X_j :

$$P(t_1, \dots, t_{j-1}, X_j) \in L[X_j].$$

It is not the zero polynomial, because if every coefficient vanished after substituting t_1, \dots, t_{j-1} , then algebraic independence of the previous tuple would force the corresponding coefficient polynomials over K to be zero, contrary to $P \neq 0$. Therefore t_j would be a root of a nonzero polynomial over L , making t_j algebraic over L . This contradicts how t_j was chosen.

By induction, after m steps we have the desired tuple. \square

4 Product projectors separating different states

Definition 4. A product vector in $H_n = (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$ is a vector of the form

$$u_1 \otimes \dots \otimes u_n, \quad u_j \in \mathbb{C}^2.$$

If every u_j is a unit vector, then

$$|u_1 \otimes \dots \otimes u_n\rangle\langle u_1 \otimes \dots \otimes u_n|$$

is a product rank-one projector.

Lemma 2. The real span of the rank-one projectors onto one-qubit unit vectors is $\text{Herm}(\mathbb{C}^2)$.

Proof. The real vector space $\text{Herm}(\mathbb{C}^2)$ has the following real basis:

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, X = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, Y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, Z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Indeed, every Hermitian 2×2 matrix has the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & c + id \\ c - id & b \end{pmatrix} = \frac{a+b}{2}I + cX - dY + \frac{a-b}{2}Z$$

with real a, b, c, d .

Now let

$$\begin{aligned} P_0 &= |0\rangle\langle 0|, & P_1 &= |1\rangle\langle 1|, \\ P_+ &= \left| \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right|, & P_{+i} &= \left| \frac{|0\rangle + i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{|0\rangle + i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right|. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$I = P_0 + P_1, \quad Z = P_0 - P_1,$$

and direct calculation gives

$$X = 2P_+ - P_0 - P_1, \quad Y = 2P_{+i} - P_0 - P_1.$$

Thus I, X, Y, Z all lie in the real span of one-qubit rank-one projectors. Hence that real span is all of $\text{Herm}(\mathbb{C}^2)$. \square

Lemma 3. *The real span of all n -qubit product rank-one projectors is $\text{Herm}(H_n)$.*

Proof. For each qubit, Lemma 2 says that $\text{Herm}(\mathbb{C}^2)$ is the real span of one-qubit rank-one projectors. The real vector space $\text{Herm}(H_n)$ is spanned by tensor products

$$A_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes A_n, \quad A_j \in \text{Herm}(\mathbb{C}^2).$$

Each A_j is a real linear combination of one-qubit rank-one projectors. Therefore each tensor product $A_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes A_n$ is a real linear combination of tensor products of one-qubit rank-one projectors, which are product rank-one projectors. Hence product rank-one projectors span $\text{Herm}(H_n)$. \square

Lemma 4. *Let $\psi, \phi \in H_n$ be unit vectors with $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| \neq |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|$. Then there is a product rank-one projector R such that*

$$\text{Tr}(R(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|)) \neq 0.$$

Proof. Set

$$\Delta = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|.$$

Then $\Delta \in \text{Herm}(H_n)$ and $\Delta \neq 0$. Suppose, for contradiction, that

$$\text{Tr}(R\Delta) = 0$$

for every product rank-one projector R . Since product rank-one projectors span $\text{Herm}(H_n)$ over \mathbb{R} , linearity of the trace would imply

$$\text{Tr}(A\Delta) = 0 \quad \text{for every } A \in \text{Herm}(H_n).$$

Taking $A = \Delta$ gives $\text{Tr}(\Delta^2) = 0$.

Because Δ is Hermitian, the spectral theorem gives an orthonormal basis of eigenvectors with real eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_D$. Therefore

$$\text{Tr}(\Delta^2) = \sum_{j=1}^D \lambda_j^2.$$

This sum is zero only if every $\lambda_j = 0$, which would mean $\Delta = 0$, contrary to $\Delta \neq 0$. Thus some product rank-one projector R must satisfy $\text{Tr}(R\Delta) \neq 0$. \square

5 Polynomial representation of local bases and Born probabilities

We now write local product bases using real parameters. For real numbers a, b , put $z = a + ib$ and define

$$e_0(a, b) = \frac{|0\rangle + z|1\rangle}{\sqrt{1 + |z|^2}}, \quad e_1(a, b) = \frac{-\bar{z}|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{1 + |z|^2}}.$$

Since $|z|^2 = a^2 + b^2$, both vectors are defined for every $(a, b) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. For every $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, the pair $\{e_0(a, b), e_1(a, b)\}$ is an orthonormal basis of \mathbb{C}^2 .

Lemma 5. *For every one-qubit unit vector u , there exist real a, b and $y \in \{0, 1\}$ such that*

$$|u\rangle\langle u| = |e_y(a, b)\rangle\langle e_y(a, b)|.$$

Proof. Write $u = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$. If $\alpha \neq 0$, set $z = \beta/\alpha$, write $z = a + ib$, and choose $y = 0$. Then

$$e_0(a, b) = \frac{|0\rangle + z|1\rangle}{\sqrt{1 + |z|^2}}$$

is a scalar multiple of $\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$, hence has the same rank-one projector.

If $\alpha = 0$, then u is a scalar multiple of $|1\rangle$. Choose $a = b = 0$ and $y = 1$. Then $e_1(0, 0) = |1\rangle$, so again the projectors agree. \square

For n qubits, let

$$t = (a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}.$$

For each bit string $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \{0, 1\}^n$, define

$$b_x(t) = e_{x_1}(a_1, b_1) \otimes \cdots \otimes e_{x_n}(a_n, b_n).$$

The local product basis associated with t is

$$B(t) = \{b_x(t) : x \in \{0, 1\}^n\}.$$

Lemma 6. *For every n -qubit product rank-one projector R , there exist $t \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ and $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$ such that*

$$R = |b_x(t)\rangle\langle b_x(t)|.$$

Proof. Write

$$R = |u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n\rangle\langle u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n|$$

with every u_j a one-qubit unit vector. By Lemma 5, for each j there exist real a_j, b_j and $x_j \in \{0, 1\}$ such that

$$|u_j\rangle\langle u_j| = |e_{x_j}(a_j, b_j)\rangle\langle e_{x_j}(a_j, b_j)|.$$

Equivalently, u_j and $e_{x_j}(a_j, b_j)$ are equal up to phase. Tensoring the n equalities shows that $u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n$ and $b_x(t)$ differ by one overall scalar of absolute value 1. Therefore their rank-one projectors are equal. \square

Definition 5 (Coefficient field). *Let S be a countable set of pure states in H_n , with one unit-vector representative chosen for each state:*

$$\psi = \sum_{s \in \{0, 1\}^n} c_s(\psi) |s\rangle.$$

Let K_S be the subfield of \mathbb{C} generated by \mathbb{Q} , by i , and by all real and imaginary parts of all coefficients $c_s(\psi)$ for all $\psi \in S$ and all bit strings s . If S is countable, then K_S is countable.

Lemma 7. *Fix n , a unit vector $\psi \in H_n$, and an outcome $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Let*

$$D(t) = \prod_{j=1}^n (1 + a_j^2 + b_j^2).$$

Then

$$q_x^\psi(t) = D(t) |\langle b_x(t), \psi \rangle|^2$$

is a polynomial in the real variables $a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n$. Its coefficients lie in the field generated by i and by the real and imaginary parts of the computational-basis coordinates of ψ .

Proof. For one qubit, the bra vectors have the form

$$\langle e_0(a, b) | = \frac{\langle 0 | + (a - ib) \langle 1 |}{\sqrt{1 + a^2 + b^2}},$$

and

$$\langle e_1(a, b) | = \frac{-(a + ib) \langle 0 | + \langle 1 |}{\sqrt{1 + a^2 + b^2}}.$$

Thus every coordinate of $\langle e_y(a, b) |$ is a polynomial in a, b , with coefficients in $\mathbb{Q}(i)$, divided by $\sqrt{1 + a^2 + b^2}$.

For n qubits, $\langle b_x(t) |$ is the tensor product of these one-qubit bras. Therefore

$$\langle b_x(t), \psi \rangle = \frac{A_x^\psi(t)}{\sqrt{D(t)}}$$

where $A_x^\psi(t)$ is a polynomial in $a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n$ with coefficients in the field generated by i and the coordinates of ψ .

Consequently

$$D(t) |\langle b_x(t), \psi \rangle|^2 = A_x^\psi(t) \overline{A_x^\psi(t)}.$$

Since conjugating $A_x^\psi(t)$ conjugates only its coefficients and replaces i by $-i$, the right-hand side is a polynomial in the real variables a_j, b_j , with coefficients in the field generated by i and the real and imaginary parts of the coordinates of ψ . This is exactly $q_x^\psi(t)$. \square

Lemma 8. *Let S be a countable set of pure states in H_n , and let K_S be its coefficient field. Let $\psi, \phi \in S$ satisfy $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| \neq |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|$. For each $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$, define*

$$h_x^{\psi, \phi}(t) = q_x^\psi(t) - q_x^\phi(t).$$

Then at least one of the polynomials $h_x^{\psi, \phi} \in K_S[a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n]$ is not the zero polynomial.

Proof. By Lemma 4, there is a product rank-one projector R such that

$$\text{Tr}(R(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|)) \neq 0.$$

By Lemma 6, there are $t' \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ and $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$ such that

$$R = |b_x(t')\rangle\langle b_x(t')|.$$

For this x ,

$$|\langle b_x(t'), \psi \rangle|^2 - |\langle b_x(t'), \phi \rangle|^2 = \text{Tr}(R(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|)) \neq 0.$$

Because $D(t') > 0$, multiplying by $D(t')$ gives

$$h_x^{\psi, \phi}(t') = D(t') (|\langle b_x(t'), \psi \rangle|^2 - |\langle b_x(t'), \phi \rangle|^2) \neq 0.$$

A polynomial that takes a nonzero value somewhere is not the zero polynomial. Hence at least one $h_x^{\psi, \phi}$ is nonzero. \square

6 Main theorem

Theorem 1. *Let S be any countable set of pure states in $H_n = (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$. Then there exists $t \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ such that the local product basis $B(t)$ is informationally complete with respect to S . Equivalently, for every $\psi, \phi \in S$,*

$$(|\langle b_x(t), \psi \rangle|^2)_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} = (|\langle b_x(t), \phi \rangle|^2)_{x \in \{0,1\}^n}$$

implies $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| = |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|$.

Proof. Choose one unit-vector representative for each pure state in S , and form the countable coefficient field K_S . By Lemma 1, choose

$$t = (a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$$

whose coordinates are algebraically independent over K_S .

Let $\psi, \phi \in S$ be distinct as pure states, meaning $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| \neq |\phi\rangle\langle\phi|$. By Lemma 8, at least one polynomial

$$h_x^{\psi, \phi} = q_x^\psi - q_x^\phi$$

is a nonzero polynomial with coefficients in K_S . Since the coordinates of t are algebraically independent over K_S , this nonzero polynomial cannot vanish at t . Thus

$$h_x^{\psi, \phi}(t) \neq 0$$

for at least one outcome x . Since $D(t) > 0$, this means

$$|\langle b_x(t), \psi \rangle|^2 \neq |\langle b_x(t), \phi \rangle|^2.$$

Therefore the two states have different probability distributions in the basis $B(t)$.

This argument applies to every distinct pair $\psi, \phi \in S$. Hence $B(t)$ is informationally complete with respect to S . \square

Corollary 1. *For every positive integer n , there exists a local product orthonormal basis B of $(\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$ such that B is informationally complete with respect to all algebraic n -qubit pure states. Thus one local measurement basis suffices.*

Remark 1. *The entire argument is not specific to pure states. The same proof applies to any countable family of density operators on H_n . One simply replaces the pure-state projector by a density operator. Thus every countable family of density operators, including the family of algebraic density operators, can be separated by one local product basis.*

Remark 2. *This proof does not bound how far apart two probability vectors must be when two algebraic states are distinct. Therefore it gives no finite-sample guarantee. It also does not give an efficient algorithm for reconstructing the state from noisy empirical frequencies. These are different, practically important tomography questions.*

7 Conclusion

We have shown that informational completeness for algebraic pure states has an unexpectedly strong local solution. For every number of qubits n , there exists a single local product orthonormal basis whose Born probability distribution distinguishes all algebraic n -qubit pure states. More

generally, the same conclusion holds for any fixed countable family of states. A single basis cannot identify an arbitrary state, but exact identifiability can become possible once the admissible family is restricted to a countable set. Thus locality, by itself, is not an obstruction to separation for algebraic states.

Our result should be interpreted as an existence result rather than as a practical tomography protocol. It does not provide a convenient finite description of the separating basis, an efficient way to implement it, or an algorithm for reconstructing the state from observed data. These limitations are especially important because countable sets can be dense among all states. Accordingly, it would be valuable to seek more explicit and operationally useful versions of the result for structured countable families such as algebraic pure states.

References

- [1] Tianfeng Feng, Tianqi Xiao, Yu Wang, Shengshi Pang, Farhan Hanif, Xiaoqi Zhou, Qi Zhao, MS Kim, and Jinzhao Sun. Two measurement bases are asymptotically informationally complete for any pure state tomography. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.17061*, 2025.
- [2] Steven T Flammia, Andrew Silberfarb, and Carlton M Caves. Minimal informationally complete measurements for pure states. *Foundations of Physics*, 35(12):1985–2006, 2005.
- [3] Leonardo Zambrano, Luciano Pereira, and Aldo Delgado. Minimal orthonormal bases for pure quantum state estimation. *Quantum*, 8:1244, 2024.